

ARRIVE 2.0 Checklist

Section/Item	Recommendation	Reported in manuscript?	Location / Notes
TITLE / ABSTRACT			
1. Title	Provide as accurate and concise a description of the content of the article as possible.	Yes	Title page
2. Abstract	Provide an accurate summary of the research objectives, animal species, key methods, principal findings and conclusions.	Yes	Abstract
INTRODUCTION			
3a. Background	Include sufficient scientific background to understand the rationale and context for the study.	Yes	Introduction
3b. Rationale	Explain how the experimental approach and animal model address the scientific objectives.	Yes	Introduction
4. Objectives	Clearly describe the research question, objectives and, where appropriate, hypotheses.	Yes	Introduction; Genome sequence report
METHODS			
5. Ethical statement	Provide the name of the ethics committee or equivalent approving body together with relevant licence or protocol numbers if applicable.	Yes	Methods: “All field procedures were conducted in strict accordance with local and international ethical guidelines. Capture and sampling were conducted under a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with the Department of National Parks and Wildlife, Malawi.”

6a. Study design	Describe the groups being compared, including control groups if relevant.	Not applicable	This study reports a reference genome assembly from a single wild-caught individual and does not involve experimental comparison groups.
6b. Experimental unit	Specify the experimental unit (e.g., single animal, litter, cage).	Yes	Methods; Table 1 – single wild-caught female individual
7a. Sample size	Specify the exact number of experimental units allocated to each group.	Yes	Methods; Genome sequence report – one female individual sequenced
7b. Sample size rationale	Explain how sample size was decided.	Not applicable	Genome assembly studies are typically performed on a single representative specimen for reference genome generation.
8a. Inclusion and exclusion criteria	Describe any criteria established a priori for including and excluding animals or data points.	Not applicable	No animals or datasets were excluded from analysis.
8b. Exclusions	Report any animals, experimental units or data points not included in the analysis and explain why.	Not applicable	No exclusions were reported.
9a. Randomisation	State whether randomisation was used to allocate experimental units.	Not applicable	This study did not involve treatment allocation or comparative experimental groups.
9b. Minimising confounders	Describe measures taken to minimise confounders.	Not applicable	No comparative intervention or

			treatment design was used.
10a. Blinding	Describe who was aware of group allocation during the experiment and analysis.	Not applicable	No group allocation or intervention comparisons were performed.
11a. Outcome measures	Clearly define all outcome measures assessed.	Yes	Genome sequence report; assembly metrics including contig N50, scaffold N50 and BUSCO completeness
11b. Primary outcome measure	Specify the primary outcome measure where appropriate.	Yes	Generation of a chromosomal-level reference genome assembly for <i>Miniopterus natalensis</i>
12a. Statistical methods	Provide details of statistical methods used for each analysis.	Not applicable	No inferential statistical analyses were performed.
12b. Unit of analysis	Specify the experimental unit used for statistical analysis.	Not applicable	No statistical analyses were conducted.
12c. Assumptions of statistical approach	Describe methods used to assess assumptions of statistical analyses.	Not applicable	No statistical analyses were conducted.
EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS			
13a. Experimental animals	Provide species-appropriate details including species, strain/subspecies, sex, age or developmental stage, and weight if relevant.	Yes	Methods; Table 1
13b. Provenance and health status	Provide additional relevant information on provenance and health/immune status if available.	Yes	Methods – wild-caught female individual from Mulanje Mountain Forest Reserve, Malawi
EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES			

14a. Experimental procedures	Describe procedures in sufficient detail to allow replication.	Yes	Methods – capture, identification, euthanasia, tissue collection, DNA extraction, sequencing and assembly procedures described
14b. Timing and frequency	Describe when and how often procedures were carried out.	Yes	Methods – capture and euthanasia performed on the same night as capture
14c. Location	Describe where procedures took place.	Yes	Methods – Mulanje Mountain Forest Reserve, Malawi
14d. Rationale for procedures	Explain why procedures were necessary.	Yes	Methods – specimen collection and tissue sampling required for reference genome sequencing
RESULTS			
15a. Results	Report summary/descriptive statistics where appropriate.	Yes	Genome sequence report; Tables 1–3
15b. Effect size	Report effect sizes with confidence intervals where appropriate.	Not applicable	No hypothesis-testing statistical analyses were performed.
DISCUSSION			
16a. Interpretation	Interpret the results taking into account study objectives and existing theory/evidence.	Yes	Introduction; Genome sequence report
16b. Study limitations	Comment on limitations of the study design and sources of bias.	Partially	Genome sequence report notes that the assembly is not fully phased.
16c. Implications	Describe implications for replacement, refinement or	Yes	Minimal handling procedures and

	reduction (the 3Rs), where relevant.		rapid humane euthanasia described in Methods.
17. Generalisability	Comment on the generalisability/translation of the findings.	Yes	Discussion throughout Introduction and Genome sequence report regarding importance for bat genomics and Bat1K initiative
18. Protocol registration	State whether a protocol was prepared and, if so, where it was registered.	No	No protocol registration applicable for this genome assembly study.
19. Data access	Provide details of where study data are available.	Yes	Data availability section; GenBank, BioProject, SRA and BioSample accession numbers provided
20. Declaration of interests	Declare any potential conflicts of interest and funding sources.	Yes	Competing Interests; Grant Information